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The Writing Ability of Early Childhood at Early Childhood Education (PAUD) in Balikpapan City

Endang Dwi Sulistyowati¹⁾, Akhmad Samsuri²⁾

¹⁾ Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Mulawarman University
Samarinda, Indonesia

E-mail: endangdwisulistyowati@yahoo.co.id

²⁾ Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Mulawarman University
Samarinda, Indonesia

E-mail: -

Abstract. Writing is one medium to communicate so that children can convey their meaning, ideas, thoughts, and feelings through meaningful words. The writing ability of childhood education can be known through every phase of development. This research was conducted at early childhood Education (PAUD) in Balikpapan city. Data collection by tests and interviews. The result showed that the ability of writing early child aged 2 to 6 years showed the existence of four categories, that is: scribble stage, linear repetitive stage, random letter stage, letter name writing or phonetic writing.

Keywords: writing ability, early childhood education (PAUD)

I. INTRODUCTION

Language is an apparatus communication fundamental to socialize and interact in the community. The language used in the people have features different. These differences caused by the presence of a variety of factors levels of society. Levels of society can be seen from the social, economic, and culture. The use of language is very important in factors social because in sociable need of language to convey an idea or ideas. People take a lot of the idea of can create in the community. The formation of an idea or ideas that draws all been concluded in education.

Montessori in Asmani (2009: 16-18) claim that education is already started since an infant born, hence babies too must be introduced in those around him, voices, objects, called kidding and conversation that they develop into children normal and healthy. In addition, the atmosphere education to be good and fitting to help children growth to create better and it is developing is in the course of the family spirit and to the principle of asih (love), grindstones, foster and (guiding), as well as to receive treatment affection, we are talking about parenting very affectionate, and in a situation of peace and harmony.

Education in the garden of childhoods can help develop varieties of potentials a good boy the psychical and physical which includes the moral and values the religion of, emotional social, cognitive, the language of, the physical condition of the motor, independence and the art of for us to enter basic education. One of the activities in motor physical to all boys and girls especially motor smooth promised to supply would be willing to write. In line with this was conducted with the, Salih (2008: 162) asserted that the operation of that a key from the growth of and child

development counseling there is among you he stimulation and moreover there is no.

Gibson in Suyanto (2005: 170) said although at the ages of 12-14 the moon kids is going to make scrawl when it is given a piece of paper and stationery while in the case of the age of 18 months kids is going to make scrawl on its own initiative. Opportunity to discuss these matters were on going and became even more obvious according to the draft bill between writing by drawing. When be mentored to be carried out efficiently, and it shall be in the age of 30 months (2,5 years) the child knows how it can write a issued in their own name.

Another argument was also raised by Mulyanti (2013: 64), habits writing that seen from father, mother and adults others will be inspired writing for children. Age 3 (three) years kids can mimicked the way people adult holding pencils although not perfect. When he was 4 (four) year old kid began to hold with perfect like adults so that can do activities such as draw or write very well.

Learning to write for their first three children early childhood education can be done by the manner of using a line help you dashed in or blank. This method is a method of old one and a lot of applied to children who just learning to 4 would be willing to write. The activities of learning that have been undertaken by children is by way of thicken a line help you dashed in or blank the shape of the letter or figures, essentially and perfectly morally good a phonetic transcription or letters hijaiyyah.

Based on the case, researchers called to do research and development on writing ability for early childhood. It is aimed to know the writing a childhood in every phase of the development. He writer raised this study entitled since writing early childhood program at the city Balikpapan

II. THE THEORY

1. The Development of A Language Children

The development of a language as one of around the basics of supposed to be possessed children, made up of several stages in accordance with the age of development and characteristics. Development is a change that lasts for life and influenced by various of mutually interact as biological, cognitive, and socio-emotional. Language is a system of symbols to communicate that includes phonology (meaning) (morphological unit, meaning) syntactic (variation, and pragmatic) (Santrock (the use of language, 1995). With the language, children can communicate mean, the purpose, thought, and the others felt about others.

A theory of the development a language that is it was commonly used as a reference in the audacity the ability of bank notes the nepali language is as follows:

1. The theory of nativisme the theory nativisme pioneered by Noam Chomsky (1974), he views that a mastery of language children are an innate by which it is affected by the development of biologically from on the part of parents. It will be said that since the end of born child have now bring an instrument called language acquisition device (LAD) or tools of language acquisition. An instrument of language acquisition this is what groups said Charlie Hebdon decision will be sent to the the development of a language the son of so that the development of a language that is owned by generally if a child is influenced by the fact that the environment.
2. Behavioristic theory put forward by B.F. Skinner different with the view put forward by Chomsky. The theory of behavioristic views that the development of a language children determined by the environment so the more children interacting with their environment and the sooner owned by the development of a language.
3. The theory of cognitive cognitive theory pioneered by Jean Piaget (1954) who consider that the development of a language for kids not influenced by congenital and environment but determined by cognitive maturity. Experts believe that the development of a language children cognitive determined by an active role in the life of the social environment in processing their information and the structure of a language. This was confirmed by Vigotsky (1986) said that between the development of a language children and cognitive development related and influenced by that culture around child brought up.

Early childhood, especially age 4-5 years could developing vocabulary an amazing. Owens (in Papalia et al) 1990. Suggested that children enrich he said the an incredibly through repetition. They are often repeating vocabulary new and unique though probably not look it. In developing the vocabulary, children use fast mapping that is a process that

the creeping the sense of the word then only hear it once or twice in conversation. In the early children these are the start combined syllables into words and words into sentence.

Of all children aged between 4-5 years rata-rata being able to use 900 until 1000 an incredibly different words. And they tapped into the 4-5 a word in one sentence that can be shaped the words of her statement, type of negative, be able to ask one, and the orders. Of all children aged between 4 years teachers have already started to being able to use the words of her a reasonable job as me cry because he is sick. At the age of their conversation was just getting started where is an incredibly a word used are more in number and more complex piece workers can. And how much to give the explanation given by a the development of a language the son of begins with a willing the development of talk, read, found herself listening to and write.

2. The Development of Talking To A Child

When children grow up and it is developing, has been an increase in in terms of either quantity or quality (the grace flexibility and due to the complexity of) tongue making a charge against product figures last week. Generation of kids able shipping companies had increased by bi rate gradually while continuing, it essentially runs up from expressing sound only, until expressing by communication of. Communication that a child may starts with uses movements and a cue to indicated its desire gradually develops into communication through speech precisely and clearly. This can be seen since the beginning of the development of where a baby issued the calling of a war understand and follow its teachings to the point where it was developed without abandoning the be a system of that the symbols the calling of a war that is meaningful. Without given a formal instructions, the son of skilled in the interpretation of phonology, morphology, syntactically, semantic, and pragmatik language. In the Indonesian economy although there was a gap in its quickness in to go on in science bank notes the nepali language, but components in a language other than there has been no change. Of the components were consisting of phonology, morphology, syntactically, of semantics and pragmatik (Bromley, 1992).

3. The Development of is Read on the Child

Raines and Canad (1990) level expressed the opinion that the process of read is not activities are to be implemented translate word for word to understand the meaning of that was found in the recitation. All of the teachers who understanding the concept of whole language will shared the view that the act of reading is a process construction does it mean to be where there are issues involving the interaction between the posts that is read of children with the experience that was ever first official quoted him.

The first step in reading is with seen something and predicts it means. The second phase is to ensure that the meaning writing which is predicted beforehand so that the obtained the decision to melancutkan reading next although there are the probability of errors in predict. The third stage is integrating new information with previous experience, an understanding of reading can be obtained after the read the whole text. Their

level of understanding children in reading is strongly influenced by the quality of predictions, samples of, and knowledge children.

4. The Development of Writing on Child

The writing is one of the media to communicate, where you can convey meaning, the idea, through the kata-kata perasaanya thoughts and meaningful. According to Poerwadarminta (1982), writing having limits as following: (1) make a phonetic, and others with a pen, lime and forth: (2) express a thought or feeling like writing, make a and others with writing in tune with the statement Badudu (1982) suggested that writing is used of pens, potlot, ball point on paper, cloth or board that produces the, words and sentences. This writing is not just to make the letters number on paper by using many an alternative media but is an effort to express feelings and thoughts that is with them individuals.

In Webster New World Dictionary (1988), writing interpreted as an activity makes patterns or wrote, the letters, or symbols in such a surface by cutting, carve or mark with a pen or a pencil. Activities writing in kindergarten have to take readiness and ripeness children. Such activities could be done if the development of motor smooth child has ripe where actually appear to be from the ability to in holds a pencil. At first only child of holding pencils to scribble, but as her an update children will concentrate the his fingers to write better. There are two the skill sets required children to write that is the ability imitate forms, and the ability move stationery.

According to Brewer, there are 4 the stages in writing ability as follows:

- a. To scribble stage of the, in the crossing out or make scratches. At this stage members of the son of are starting to make by means of a utensil level playing field wrote. At this stage members of they only learn about the language writing competition and journalism in the manner of do from a written note reflected the bank sound assets.
- b. Linear repetitive stage of the, in the the repetition of a linear. At this stage members of the son of trace the shape of a piece of writing that horizontally.
- c. Random a letter stage of the, in the writing random. During the preparatory phase of this child learns about a variety of forms of which it is an writings and took the children of israel different words on the great commission nor the words of her.
- d. A letter namewriting persons of very writing a phonetic, in the writing the name. At this stage members of the son of began to formulate and connecting between the posts and its sound. The son of started to write the name of and the whirring noise made at the same time.

Morrow (1993) his hand has portioned edom since writing the son to be 6 steps:

- a. Writing via drawing, promised to supply writing with how to draw
- b. Writing via scribbling manner, promised to supply write by way of were to stroke. The son of a lot of times when crossing out towards the left without his leave equity on the right hand as if he were trying take examples from a written note of the adult population is writing

- c. Reporting via making letter-like for, promised to supply write by way of making the form like the letter. The child does not only make scratches, but it has been is involving him to up his game
- d. Writing via reproducing well-learned unit or letter stings, namely write by way of produce the letters or units are good. Children writing the letters with follow for example tried to write down his name.
- e. Writing via invented spelling, that is writing by trying to spell one by one. In this stage boy tried to spell by means of try wrong
- f. Writing via conventional spelling, namely write by way of spell directly. In this stage child has can spell is right both in terms of the arrangement of.

Feldman (1991) gave them different restrictions about the stages to go on in science writing ability as follows:

- a. To scribble on the page, promised to supply make scratches on paper. At this stage the removal the son of make an image on the great commission that is separated.
- b. Copy of spoken word pieces, pt pgn promised to supply modeled after the th letter. The son of have become intrigued to modeled after as in a word mama, papa and so forth. Invented selected, promised to supply learn to spell. At this stage the removal the son of start finding ways to spell and i wrote out letters according to came to me saying.

Of some opinion put forward by some of about stages writing ability that will be used for as a reference in this research activity is the judgement Brewer that divides writing ability to 4 a stage in as follows:

- a. Stage to scribble stage, namely the crossing out or make scratches.
- b. Linear repetitive stage, namely stage repetition linear. At the this child trace the shape of writing that horizontal.
- c. Random a letter stage, namely stage writing random. At this stage child learns about the various shape that is a the literature and repeat different words or sentence.
- d. Random a letter stage, namely stage writing random. At this stage child learns about the various shape that is a the literature and repeat different words or sentence.

Letter name writing or a phonetic writing, namely stage write a name. At the this child began to formulate and links between the literature and saying. Children start writing the name and sound simultaneously.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. The Kind of Research

The kind of research will be done is research descriptive qualitative. The qualitative study according to Bogdan and Taylor (in Sujarweni, 2014: 19) explained that the data descriptive can be greeting or the literature and behavior those who observed. In this case the data were drawn of writing ability early childhood. A qualitative approach is expected to produce the quality of the shape of the early childhood in the city Balikpapan. Place research in this research would yield a

description of of ability writing early childhood aged 2 to 6 years.

2. The Place of Research

Research would be conducted in an institution of early childhood education paud in the city of will be for Balikpapan. Of institutions to provide assistance of early childhood education paud would otherwise be selected out who having the place of a child care service from , play groups , and kindergarten. It is aimed the can be obtained this official data on writing ability of a child with her every phase the development of 2 age of the total up to 6 years.

3. Data Collection Method

a. Test method

Test will be used to see writing ability early childhood in the city Balikpapan. Every child will be an assignment to write individually. In its implementation researchers assisted by teachers paud who follow in the classroom targeted research.

b. Interview a method

This interview shall be done for teachers of early childhood education paud and students parents to obtain information about the process of learning to write at the school. While the objective of the interview to parents who do not used to obtain information about the habit of learning to write in the house of.

IV. RESEARCH RESULT

The results of the study conforms to the theory of put forward by brewer that are categorized writing ability a panorama of the four phases step is to scribble stage of the , linear repetitive stage of the , random latter stage of the , a letter name writing persons of very writing a phonetic , the results of research conducted in the city of will be for Balikpapan study also found some ability a writing a usia dini early childhood education 2 old son adrien agreed that second biggest investor in indonesia with 6 years shows that there has been the four categories of reflected the bank sound asset. After going through the process of of the data analysis found the four categories of as follows:

1. Stage to scribble

Stage from 31 son who is a respondents research between the ages of two to six years is as follows:

- a. Children ages 2 years as many as declared seven children,
- b. Children ages 4 as many as 11th son of
- c. Children ages 5 years as many as 6 people
- d. The age of 6 years as many as 2 people

2. Linear stage repetitive

Stage like stage to scribble stage , at the next is the stage linear repetitive there are 19 people with details as follows:

- a. Children age 4 years as many as 13 people
 - b. Children aged six years by one children
- ### 3. The stage of random latter

Stage of the during the preparatory phase of is found as many as 13 passenger with details as follows:

- a. The age of three year is about 1 kid on the way
- b. Were four years old as many as 3 kid on the way
- c. Five years of age as many as 8 kid on the way
- d. Six years of age as many as 1 kid on the way

4. Stage a letter name writing or a phonetic
Writing at this stage there were 26 people with details as follows:

- a. The age of four years old found four children
 - b. The age of five years old found 15 children
- Six years of age 7 children

V. CONCLUDING

Although the ability early childhood in wrote it following in order the ability according to the theory the development of writing ability in general it can be said that since writing early childhood always starts of the stage to scribble stage then increase in stage linear repetitive stage, random latter stage , and last at the letter name writing or a phonetic writing. When views based on the age , for the to scribble stage not just reached by the son the age of 2 years. From 31 son who is a respondents research three-year-old are still at the to scribble stage as many as seven kids , children ages 4 years is still in to scribble stage as many as 11th son of while children ages 5 years are still produce the rest of the stage scrabble stage as many as 6 people. For children aged 6 years are still is that produces the rest of the stage to scribble stage as many as two people.

Like stage to scribble stage , at the next namely linear repetitive also found in some age of three years up to 6 years. Although in generally stage linear repetitive reached by children aged three years , but was also found children aged 2 years have got to the repetitive as many as six children. So for the linear repetitive can also reached by children aged three years as many as 13 people and was a age of 6 years be at the linear repetitive as many as one. The highest stage for its stages writing ability early childhood is the stage a letter name writing or a phonetic writing. This stage found only for children aged three years up to 6 years.

The result of this research also found there are several children who are still 4 years old but have can produce a few letters almost form of a word while of that age teachers have not teach forms letters. It turns out that the results of interviews with their parents, they are taught first although teachers have not teach read and write. Motivation parents when teach read and write triggered absence of the sense of worry when the child will enter primary school. There were several schools that to enter primary school should have can read and write letters in indonesian language.

The phase that be the reference could not adapted by age because they were not age which is used to to measures the but the quality of developept children must be trained babies to can pass through that have been over explain by brewer. Divided based on domain reflect put forward by bloomfill writing ability including in the domain of skill. To improved

the skills of have need of exercise repeated. The more trained so skill writing will increase hence parents should be introduce the rudiments writing ability early. This having been demonstrated through the research activity that do in the city Balikpapan in various institutions paud.

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